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Governance Issues and Environmental Impacts of Oil Palm Plantations in Riau (A Green Criminology Overview)

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Abstract

Indonesia, as an agrarian country, has a wealth of natural resources that can be used to meet human needs, either directly or indirectly through economic activities. One of the initiatives done is through the growth of oil palm farms, which is increasing in pace with global demand. Riau Province owns the majority of Indonesia's oil palm plantation land. Palm oil is a significant commodity in Riau, and with first-rate production, Riau Province can be considered a national center for oil palm development. This article will discuss two major aspects of oil palm plantations in Riau. First, it is concerned with the multiple detrimental effects of oil palm plantations in Riau, both environmental and socioeconomic. Second, this study will discuss several concerns concerning the governance of oil palm plantations in Riau. This study employs qualitative research methodologies, with a literature review serving as the primary data collection method. In this study, the literature review refers to gathering information from multiple books, journal articles, regulations, and other supporting papers. A literature review is conducted to examine prior studies on environmental criminality, green criminology, oil palm plantations, and oil palm plantation management in Riau. Finally, three conclusions are proposed in this study. The first conclusion is about the conflicting laws and regulations. In Indonesia, laws in the form of exemptions or permits must seek *rechtsbeginsel*, which must be rational or logical. Based on the nature of the prior first difficulty, the second conclusion speaks to the nature of bureaucracy. Bureaucracy with a criminogenic nature allows for the growth of forms of power abuse and maladministration. Since this deviation can cause harm, it is classified as a crime. In this situation, there is both social and environmental harm. The third conclusion in this discussion is the vulnerability to abuse of power as a result of power distribution. As a result, especially in the context of the oil palm plantation crisis, the end of the fraud committed by private investors that should be rectified by the political elite will not be fixed: it will reoccur as a true result of terrible governance practices carried out compactly.

Keywords: Palm Oil Plantation Governance, Green Criminology, Environmental Harm, Social Harm

1. Introduction

Indonesia, as an agrarian country, has a wealth of natural resources that can be used to meet human needs, either directly or indirectly through economic activities. One of the initiatives done is through the growth of oil palm

farms, which is increasing in pace with global demand. The distribution of these plantation crops in Indonesia has covered practically all of the major islands, with the extent and distribution of the area expanding year after year. The island of Sumatra has the most oil palm crops (64%), followed by Kalimantan (31%). The majority of Sumatra's oil palm plantations expanded in Riau, where the pattern revealed that smallholder plantations were widely developed plantations (Li, 2015). Riau Province owns the majority of Indonesia's oil palm plantation land. Palm oil is another important item in Riau (BPS Jakarta, 2008 Chalid, 2011, p.79). Riau Province, with a first-rate output level, can be considered a national center for oil palm development (Tempo, August 10, 2007, in Sachih, 2008, p.1-2).

Table 1 shows the distribution of oil palm plantation acreage in numerous Indonesian provinces, with Riau ranking first with the largest and highest production.

Table 1: Distribution of Oil Palm Plantations in Indonesia in 2020

PROVINCE	LARGE	PRODUCTION
Riau	2.850.003	9.775.672
Central Kalimantan	1.714.660	8.298.584
North Sumatera	1.630.744	6.601.399
South Sumatera	1.196.915	4.365.004
East Kalimantan	1.492.934	4.331.930
West Kalimantan	1.904.015	3.551.825
Jambi	1.086.623	3.096.621
South Kalimantan	564.632	1.667.132
West Sumatera	390.554	1.390.199
Total	12.831.080	43.078.366

Source: Directorate General of Plantations, 2021

According to data from the Ministry of Agriculture's Directorate General of Plantations, palm oil production in 2020 is expected to reach 49.11 million tons, with average productivity of 3,568 Kg/Ha/Y. People's oil palm farms produce 17.35 million tons of CPO, while state-owned oil palm plantations produce 2.47 million tons and the private sector provides 29.27 million tons. As demonstrated in Table 1.2, the land area grows at a rate ranging from 5% to 6% every year.

Table 2: Area of Oil Palm Plantations in Indonesia 2011-2020

YEAR	LARGE OF THE AREA (Ha)				GROWTH SPEED (%)
	PR	PN	PS	TOTAL	
2011	3.752.480	678.378	4.561.966	8.992.824	7,24
2012	4.137.620	683.227	4.751.868	9.572.715	6,45
2013	4.356.087	727.767	5.381.166	10.465.020	9,32
2014	4.422.365	729.022	5.603.414	10.754.801	4,69
2015	4.535.400	743.894	5.980.982	11.260.277	8,82
2016	4.739.318	707.428	5.754.719	11.201.465	6,92
2017	5.697.892	638.143	7.712.687	14.048.722	6,50
2018	5.818.888	614.756	7.892.706	14.326.350	1,98
2019	6.035.742	627.042	8.061.636	14.724.420	2,78
2020	6.090.883	643.888	8.261.639	14.996.010	1,81
GROWTH SPEED AVERAGE (%)					5,65

Source: Directorate General of Plantations, 2021

Then, according to Sawit Watch (2015), one of the NGOs monitoring the Indonesian palm oil business, up to 2014, Indonesia generated around 27.1 million tons of CPO annually. Whereas roughly 20% is used for internal needs, the majority is shipped to countries with the world's largest palm oil markets, especially China, India, and the European Union. Furthermore, the average annual growth rate of CPO export volume was 12.94% from 2003 to

2014, with an annual increase in export value of 25.76%. In 2013, palm oil commodity exports were 20.58 million tons of CPO and other products worth USD 15.84 billion. Until September 2014, for example, shipments totaled 15.96 million tons valued at \$12.75 million. This condition makes Indonesia the largest producer and exporter of palm oil in the world (Sawit Watch, 2015).

Furthermore, the conversion of oil palm plantation areas to oil palm utilization influences both natural and human resources. The influence of oil palm is polarized, with various research revealing both good and negative effects. According to Syahza, Nasrul, and Irianti (2020), oil palm has several advantages, including contributing to the economy and raising the welfare index of rural people. According to the data, the welfare index increased by 0.16 between 2016 and 2018. This means that the well-being of rural communities grew by 16% between 2016 and 2018, compared to the prior period. Oil palm activities have a positive external impact and can be stated to be helpful for the surrounding environment, including, among other things, boosting rural welfare, opening up employment and commercial prospects in rural regions, and contributing to regional development. On the other hand, oil palm activities have an impact on the community's socioeconomic and cultural aspects, such as the availability of infrastructure facilities that can be used by the local community, such as roads, schools, houses of worship, and village markets, as well as the availability of agricultural workforce education, health education, primary and secondary education. In keeping with the findings above, Soedomo (2019) did a study on the growth of Teluk Pulai Village in Kalimantan, concluding that the economic prospects improved after the establishment of oil palm plantations. Teluk Pulai Village previously had poor economic prospects and lacked the amenities and infrastructure to let its residents expand their businesses. There was an increase in livelihoods and higher and more steady incomes once the oil palm company began operations in Teluk Pulai Village. Villagers in Sungai Melayu Village, Kalimantan, felt a good influence as well, with a major improvement in the economy. These economic advantages enable farming households to increase their public consumption. Some agricultural products that were previously uneconomical to market have become more cost-effective. As a result, peasants have become more market-oriented, which creates additional cash for the community. As previously stated, the good and bad repercussions of oil palm plantation development in Indonesia are polarized, but not evenly dispersed. This condition is demonstrated by Obidzinski et al. (2012), who discovered that economic advantages were not evenly dispersed in their research in Indonesia. Traditional/customary landowner stakeholders, for example, have faced constraints on traditional land use rights and land loss. Many researchers discovered a rise in land scarcity, an increase in land prices, and land conflicts in all studied areas (Obidzinski, et al., 2012). As a result, it can be stated that several parties, mainly the local community, are hurt or do not receive their rights in this case. Furthermore, Obidzinski et al. (2012)'s study is one of many that show that oil palm plantations have a major negative influence on the environment as well as the social, cultural, and political areas of society. From an environmental standpoint, oil palm plants require 1.25 to 2.31 mm of water per day and may absorb water to a depth of 5.2 m. (Dufrene et al, 1993). Because oil palm trees deplete groundwater, oil palm plantations can impair groundwater resources for crops other than oil palm (Kallarackal et al., 2004). This makes it incredibly difficult for people to get safe drinking water. State losses, on the other side, can result from a lack of significant treatment of environmental crimes. The Center for International Forestry Research (CIFOR) researched to investigate how existing public rules and standards are claimed to solve three significant performance gaps impacting the coconut sector of Indonesian palm oil. The results demonstrate that policy implementation has not been effective, particularly for enterprises that do not comply with regulations. It was discovered that the interaction between state national regulations and private standards remained adversarial (Dayne, 2018). In terms of implementation and enforcement, "antagonism" can relate to how weak governance and corruption impede complete implementation (Luttrell et al., 2018). The above conditions represent a type of green criminology study, according to a criminology review.

So, based on the explanation above, this study will focus on two major aspects of oil palm plantations in Riau. First, it is concerned with the multiple detrimental effects of oil palm plantations in Riau, both environmental and socioeconomic. Second, this study will discuss several concerns concerning the governance of oil palm plantations in Riau. This component, the author believes, may be one of the reasons why, even though the effects of oil palm farms in Riau are genuine, numerous measures to mitigate them frequently fail. Furthermore, according to green criminology, environmental crime is related to the utilization of natural resources that ultimately produce harm to nature itself and mankind.

2. Method

This article employed qualitative research methodologies because they allow researchers to investigate social and cultural issues. The qualitative technique is a type of social action that stresses how people interpret and comprehend their experiences to comprehend the individual's social reality. Qualitative approaches are interested in beliefs, experiences, and meanings derived from personal experiences (Haradhan, 2018). Furthermore, the research method used is explanatory research. De Vaus (2002) distinguishes two categories of study based on their goals. The particular measures that the researcher must take to attain the research objectives. Examining numerous variables and conditions of environmental criminality in oil palm farms and their relationship to issues of governance of oil palm plantations, particularly in Riau, is one aspect of explanatory research in the framework of this study. In this regard, this research question begins with the question "why," followed by "how," to aid in making decisions on the topic and direction of study in clearly overcoming its boundaries (Blaikie, 2007). This paper used a literature review as a data gathering technique, specifically materials gathered from government agencies and non-governmental organizations that focus on environmental issues and environmental crimes. In this study, the literature review refers to gathering information from multiple books, journal articles, regulations, and other supporting papers. A review of the literature serves as the foundation for considerable and meaningful study. A literature review was used to determine what past research has done, what additional study is required, to identify variables related to the phenomena, and to identify the relationship between theory/concept and practice (Onwuegbuzie, Leech, and Collins, 2012). In connection with this research, a literature review is used to look at previous research related to environmental crime, green criminology, oil palm plantations, and management of oil palm plantations in Riau.

3. Results And Discussion

3.1. Green Criminology Review on the Negative Impacts of Oil Palm Plantation

According to the previous explanation, the use of oil palm has both beneficial and bad consequences. In these circumstances, the State, as a responsible actor in natural resource management, must be able to control the possible environmental and socioeconomic repercussions of oil palm plantations. The scenarios for mitigating potential consequences are typically in the form of legislation and policies. As previously stated, there are numerous regulations and policies in place to control the possible environmental and social implications of oil palm cultivation.

Regulations and policies can be classified as patterns of formal reaction in the context of dealing with crime from a criminological standpoint (Mustofa, 2007). Efforts to enforce environmental regulations are controlled as a type of formal reaction under Law Number 32 of 2009 about Environmental Protection and Management (UUPPLH), which provides three forms of law enforcement, namely administrative, civil, and criminal law enforcement. However, according to Dayne (2018), the implementation of environmental policies and regulations needs to be enhanced because deviations that can affect humans and the environment continue to be discovered.

According to the discussion of the green criminology study, this oil palm plantation operation can be considered an environmental crime due to its influence on the ecosystem. Environmental crime, often known as green crime, is defined by criminological research as human behaviors that misuse ecosystems and natural resources for their own sake and cause environmental damage (Beirne & South, 2007; Stretesky, 2013 in Lynch, 2020). This environmental damage will therefore have an impact on human life as well as other species such as plants and animals (White, 2008).

In the palm oil phenomenon, there are dynamics involving good and negative repercussions. Different perspectives on this phenomenon influence efforts to mitigate potential environmental repercussions. Many groups of people continue to exploit nature as much as possible, without preserving the environment. Instead, the exploitation is to perpetuate the positive impact of oil palm. Therefore, green criminology sees the tendency of damage to the ecological system to increase or support production, this is seen as a tendency to damage ecologically capitalism.

By using the treadmill of production approach, green criminology can be identified with ecological disorganization where human activities reduce conditions and force ecosystems to deteriorate. When pollution is introduced into an ecosystem or available resources are removed from nature for production, ecological disorder emerges (Lynch, 2020).

In addition to investigating oil palm plantation practices that may cause environmental damage. Green criminology also describes environmental economic crimes, one of which is related to palm oil extraction. Furthermore, there is a political economy relationship in the phenomenon of oil palm expansion, which borrows from Long et al. (2012) apply a theoretical model, namely the treadmill of production, examining how environmental damage is a direct result of the production process, growth, and capital accumulation, which is supported by the alignment of corporate and state interests (in Ruggiero & South, 2013). Instead of promoting economic progress, it harms the environment and depletes natural resources.

The collaboration of legitimate and illegal entrepreneurs with the state is a fundamental feature of this sort of environmental crime (Ruggiero & South, 2013). This relates to the risks associated with palm oil production, which can be evident in practice, rhetoric, and relationships on the ground, all of which reflect larger structures of power and control. The claim of the economics and agro-industry as a feasible solution to alleviate poverty and enhance living standards is part of a bigger form of ecological and power relations exploitation (Mol, 2017). Given these economic and agricultural claims, policymakers create regulations to control potential environmental impacts associated with palm oil production, such as the issuance of the Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil (RSPO) certificate, which aims to develop and implement global standards for sustainable palm oil production. The RSPO, on the other hand, is recognized to have failed to address the greater power asymmetry in palm oil production. Instead, the RSPO has aided in the consolidation of export-oriented palm oil firms and non-governmental organizations (Pichler, 2013).

Furthermore, the RSPO's composition prioritizes commercial interests in export-oriented palm oil firms and downstream industries throughout the chain in terms of power relations and strategic selectivity. As a result, transnational palm oil conglomerates in Southeast Asia agreed to apply selective environmental and social criteria (such as avoiding fires in land clearing, compensating for customary lands, or creating wildlife corridors for endangered species) to maintain market access, particularly in Europe. These certification and labeling procedures, however, do not cover all parties, resulting in institutional and strategic discrimination against plantation workers, smallholders, and indigenous peoples where these factors structurally marginalize plantation work (Pichler, 2013). In addition to the types of environmental crimes, green criminology has special attention to the implementation of public policies. Where, it is often found that the implementation of criminogenic public policies is carried out by corrupt governments, companies, and organized crime (Ruggiero & South, 2013). In the context of this research, various policies in the context of managing oil palm plantations contain various loopholes for the emergence of crime.

As previously stated, the implementation of oil palm policies in Indonesia creates opportunities for environmental crime. Whereas rules governing sustainable palm oil are densely packed with laws and legal procedures. At all levels, many new regulations are being developed. However, the multiple contradictory regulations create a confused and fragmented picture of responsibility (especially at the central to local government levels). Given the absence of clear authority and the inadequate enforcement context, a better constructed legal or regulatory structure does not always result in better outcomes. Many regulations create ambiguity and provide options for businesses to avoid complying with existing regulations (Luttrell, et al., 2018).

Law enforcement agencies, on the other hand, are weak, and authorities may not always have clear power or ability to enforce sanctions. In this setting, the value of additional regulatory development is called into doubt. Whereas the corporation criticizes the government for a lack of regulation, even though there are numerous regulations, the government cannot oversee them (Luttrell, et al, 2018). For example, despite the company's commitment to No Deforestation, No Peat, No Exploitation (NDPE), the policy is not always followed (Dayne, 2018).

3.2. Palm Oil Plantation Governance Issues in Riau

Various negative impacts of oil palm plantations in Riau that appear to be ignored and repeated, in the author's opinion, indicate a weakness in formal legal regulations related to environmental management, both national and regional levels as if ignoring the impact of environmental damage caused by human behavior, whether carried out on a small or large scale (by corporations). As stated in the State Minister of Environment Regulation No. 10 of 2010 on Mechanisms for Preventing Pollution and Environmental Damage Caused by Forest/Land Fires. Article 4 paragraph (1) means that customary law communities may clear land by burning with a maximum land area of 2 (two) hectares per family head for planting native types, with the obligation to notify the village head. The rule further states that land burning licenses are not permitted in situations of little rainfall, a lengthy dry season, or a dry environment. This provision is intended to provide chances for local communities to manage natural resources, however, it will influence environmental harm, particularly due to a lack of government oversight.

Meanwhile, the Riau Provincial Government released Governor Regulation Number 15 of 2010 regarding Amendments to the Riau Governor's Regulation Number 52 of 2008 concerning Guidelines for Land Clearing and Yards for Communities in Riau. Article 1 expressly permits land clearing by burning trees; of course, this causes air pollution and environmental damage, both to process natural resources and for other purposes. The legislation also states that land burning is permitted based on the accumulation of specific areas in each location, as stated in Article 1 paragraph 4.

This rule is very likely to allow companies to exploit and engage in reckless behavior, such as working with local communities to extend land and minimize land clearance costs by burning land. As a result, Central Kalimantan's total area in 2015 was 15.3 million hectares, of which 12.7 hectares (78%) were managed by plantation corporations (Djumaty & Dey, 2015).

The above-mentioned Governor of Riau Regulation Number 52 of 2008 is identical to pseudo-policy. Rather than benefiting local communities, it enables firms to accommodate the expansion and exploitation of oil palm farms. The regulation demonstrates that current environmental policy does not prioritize the restoration of environmental sustainability (Pease, 1998). By examining the significant interaction that exists between the state and businesses in the phenomena of environmental crime. The discovery of recurring environmental and social repercussions of oil palm plantations in Riau Province in the middle of existing governance that has been governed in a succession of laws and regulations sparked this topic.

Hamilton-Hart suggests that there is a risk of misgovernance in the overall implementation of oil palm certification policies, due to differences in implementation between the central, provincial, district, and local governments. This illustrates when the local government system is unable to incorporate central government policies into its regulatory system or is unable to convey its policy objectives to the public (Hamilton-Hart, 2014).

Many effects of territorialization have occurred in the regions since the implementation of a policy. Territorialization arises through strategic and operational processes related to the construction and application of procedural rules and regulations. Territorialization also occurs through rules and policy-making processes involving socio-technological processes linked to the spirit of a managerial approach to sustainability. The implementation of a policy will make people feel pressured by feelings of being forced, co-opted, or dominated by external forces. People are forced to do whatever the authorities want, even though they have no problem at all. The community must also give up their assets to be confiscated as well if there is a potential that is assumed to be detrimental to the authorities. Furthermore, the community also has a great potential to be harmed on their land, because they do not have any power at all (Ruysschaert, 2016). Various studies have shown that certain elements impede the seamless accessibility of itself for all "controlled" parties involved in the context of the Regional Government's authority in the PKS governance process. First, the geographical element will be linked to identification (Sikor & Lund, 2009). Identity becomes something embedded in a material, both living and non-living. The embedded identity in this context is the administrative area's identity. The challenge is that the administrative area cannot be described simply as a physical border established by the State; in actuality, this identity also tightly controls which regions are controlled by whom, who has the right to access them and for what

purposes the territory may be used. These three facts are only known to the authorities. These three facts, on the other hand, cannot be known in detail by the controlled party.

The second component is the knowledge component. Knowledge may be defined as any valuable knowledge that is kept in one's cognitive mind (Peluso & Lund, 2011). It is believed that the cognitive mind that has been filled will be able to perpetuate the next virtuous advantage, which is correctly motivating conduct or delivering benefits for himself and others in his life. However, the masters themselves are unsure of what relevant knowledge should be delivered in this setting. Doubts over who owns the territory of Rohul and Rohil force those in power to tread carefully before taking any action. Yet, strangely, it is preferable not to have to perform unnecessary things.

Finally, social ties are an important aspect of this situation. Social relations are complex that arise as a result of ongoing social interaction between numerous parties involved in a certain topic. A specific problem that all persons involved in it must be aware of. As a result, culture or culture, conventions, administrative processes, circumstances, events, and so on constitute the context's binding (Kinseng, 2017). Again, because the governing party only wants to build and maintain social relationships with parties that it finds profitable (read: capable of assisting in the maintenance of accessibility exclusively for itself), the party under its control will be excluded from the social connection. Instead of when social relations occur, social actions that are usually applied are dissociative social actions that give rise to social disintegration dictions such as contradictions to social conflicts (Abdulkadir-Sunito, Adiwibowo, Soetarto, Kinseng, & Foley, 2017). Corporate misconduct, often known as corporate malpractice, is a business behavior that undermines legality and becomes an adversary to socioeconomic justice (Wibisono, 2007). Misappropriating legal authorities, bribing state officials, tax fraud, and writing and following "rubber" rules and regulations are all examples of actions that can undermine legality. That is, such a nature is the production of the most recent article product following the occurrence of a criminal crime that is controlled in such a manner that only the perpetrator benefits. the antagonistic nature of the socioeconomic justice in question is that it can be done in a variety of ways, such as closing public access to the traded investment land, accusing and punishing anyone who is not proven to have stolen assets, doing illegal logging, and/or burning land without a permit. It should also be highlighted that, anthropologically, the author's last point has the potential to cause discord over local citizens' ulayat rights.

3. Conclusion

As discussed, various issues concerning the regulation of oil palm farms and their influence on the environment in Riau can be viewed as complicated phenomena. As a consequence, this study will conclude with some conclusions that will validate the findings of the preceding debate. The first conclusion is about the conflicting laws and regulations. In Indonesia, laws in the form of exemptions or permissions must seek *rechtsbeginsel*, which must be rational or logical. To prevent meaninglessness, double meaning, or ambiguity, as well as insufficient explanations, legal sources and their derivations must have relevance, importance, and solid descriptions. A violation of this principle can occur for four reasons: (1) There are still issues in the stages of national law. This is intended by the interpretation of the parties in charge of deriving articles from statutory rules, such that when there is a misconcentration, there will be disharmony between the newest article's execution and the 1945 Constitution; (2) There are still issues in the bill's phases. This is implied by corrupt acts between authorities and authorities to carry out plans that will one day only safeguard them all; (3) Citizens' engagement in the law remains low. Citizens are supposed to be able to participate in both national legislation and the enactment of laws constitutionally. Because citizens are the most susceptible subjects to legal infractions. This is also what leads to many citizens becoming criminals, even though they are victims in certain oil palm instances; and, (4) the incidence of ineffectiveness non the DPR's plenary actions. The actions of the DPR plenary session are widely known to employ the most recent articles, which are out of date, have no modifications, and only benefit specific parties (Lobubun, Raharusun, & Anwar, 2022).

Based on the nature of the prior first difficulty, the second conclusion speaks to the nature of bureaucracy. It is his criminogenic disposition that allows for the creation of forms of power abuse and maladministration. Since this deviation might cause harm, it is classified as a crime. Environmental harm means "environmental damage," and this term is frequently used by scholars when analyzing the influence on the environment. Environmental harm is

a contentious notion. This is due to the fact that the definition of harm utilized is frequently a legal and legal meaning. However, the concept of environmental harm utilized by academics in its development is becoming more prevalent, and it does not rely solely on legal and legal definitions (White, 2011).

The study of environmental damage is based on an examination of societal harm or social injury. This is because the study of social harm covers a wide range of human losses and is not restricted by legal or legal considerations (White, 2013). The distinction is that overall socioeconomic disadvantage targets the full range of human needs and rights, whereas environmental degradation addresses species other than humans as well as people themselves (White, 2014). Accordingly, environmental harm is concerned with the health and well-being of humans, the environment, animals, and plants (White, 2022). In his discussion of environmental damage, he talks about environmental degradation. Environmental degradation is the depletion of natural resources, ecosystem damage, habitat destruction, extinction of environmental animals, and pollution (Johnson, et al., 1997).

Environmental damage, like social harm, is a societal structural problem. This is because the person in control of this phenomenon is not only where huge corporations are, but people also play a part in this phenomenon (White, 2014). According to White (2010), environmental damage is genuinely ecological harm that has a detrimental impact on people, the biosphere, and species. The examination of environmental damage in a normative criminological debate examines ecological issues such as how human activities generate both significant and little environmental damage.

In the subject of green criminology, two definitions of environmental harm are clarified. First, some changes are harmful to humans, the environment, and animals. Second, environmental damage is caused by the state, companies, and those in power, who can modify the definition of environmental crimes to justify environmentally detrimental behaviors. The second definition by White (2022) stresses how the acts of power parties are compared to individuals as environmental agents. Green criminology employs these two criteria when discussing perpetrators and victims. Environmental harm affect both humans and the environment, as well as animals, plants, and other species, with a focus on those in power. Individuals as actors, according to green criminology, have a relationship with the prevailing mode of production and class disparities, such that the biggest culprits of environmental destruction remain the governing party (White, 2022).

The conclusion in this discussion is the susceptibility to misuse of power as a result of power distribution. This debate raises the prospect that establishing lobby spaces at the regional level will be more relevant if done at the central level and vice versa. Because of the restricted pattern of people's engagement, the lobby space can only be wide open for those controlling parties (Hadi, 2019). People or individuals may only express their political desires through restricted events related to the implementation of public policies, which are ironically only held at regional general elections or post-conflict municipal elections. Adopting a quasi-referendum system results in "representatives" of the public interest being granted complete authority solely to public officials. Therefore, especially in the context of the oil palm plantation crisis, the end of the fraud perpetrated by private investors that should be rectified by the political elite will not be fixed: it will reoccur as a true result of terrible governance practices carried out compactly. This is referred to as plebiscitary leadership democracy (Held, 1987).

There are also three issues discovered when examining the expansion of the stakeholder ranks and the growing number of interest groups. The first question is how equal opportunity for economic advancement will complicate administrative policies in practice. According to the 1945 Constitution, the Republic of Indonesia is required to provide equal distribution of opportunity in the form of economic progress for all Indonesians. To carry it out further, the State must allow each Regional Government to carry out its management activities through regional autonomy. Given that each regional government has lived and worked in their separate areas, the implementation of regional autonomy is considered to produce a more effective and efficient implementation performance. Local governments are therefore considered to be the most knowledgeable actors and are aware that each region's challenges are inherent in that region. The issue is that the management rules that are in place burden the administrative order. The implementation of economic equity inevitably comes to a halt on its administrative bounds as a result of the numerous parties involved. As a result of the first issue, which is the creation of coalitions or alignments amongst rulers who do not wish to prioritize the interests of local citizens and/or customs, this will continue to the following issue. Finally, the creation of "little kings" in each region makes this problem worse.

The data that surfaced were from indigenous peoples and they were a part of the poor governance practiced by the authorities and corporations.

References

- Abdulkadir-Sunito, M., Adiwibowo, S., Soetarto, E., Kinseng, R. A., & Foley, S. (2017). The Limit to Politics of Ethnicity? Migration and Upland Transformation in Central Sulawesi. *Sodality*, 5(3), 226-233.
- Blaikie, N. (2007). *Approaches to social enquiry: advancing knowledge*. London: Polity Press.
- Chalid, N. (2011). Perkembangan Perkebunan Kelapa Sawit di Provinsi Riau [Oil Palm Plantations Development in Riau Province]. *Jurnal Ekonomi*, 19, 78-97.
- Dayne, S. (2018). *Governing sustainable palm oil in Indonesia: An evolving policy regime*. Accessed through <https://forestsnews.cifor.org/58479/governing-sustainable-palm-oil-in-indonesia-hiatus-leads-to-change?fnl=en> on 26th May 2022
- De Vaus, D. (2002). *Research design in social research*. London: Sage Publications.
- Djumaty, B, L. Dey, N, P, H. (2015). Dilema Kebijakan Yang Pro Rakyat (Peraturan Gubernur Kalimantan Tengah No 15 Tahun 2010 tentang Pembukaan Lahan dan Pekarangan Bagi Masyarakat) [Pro-People Policy Dilemma (Governor of Central Kalimantan Regulation No. 15 of 2010 regarding Opening of Land and Yard for the Community)]. *KRITIS*, XXIV(2), 160-176.
- Dufrene, E., Dubos, B., Rey, H., Quencez, P., & Saugier B. (1993). Changes in Evapotranspiration from an Oil Palm Stand (*Elaeis guineensis* Jacq.) Exposed to Seasonal Soil Water Deficits. *Oleagineux*, 48(3): 105-120.
- Hadi, K. (2019). Perbandingan Penegakan Demokrasi di Indonesia Pasca-Rezim Suharto dan Filipina Pasca-Rezim Marcos [Upholding Democracy Comparison in Indonesia Post-Soeharto Regime and Phillipines Post Marcos-Regimes]. *Insignia Journal of International Relations*, 6(1), 13-29.
- Hamilton-Hart, N. (2014). Monetary Politics in Southeast Asia: External Imbalances in Regional Context. *New Political Economy*, 19(6), 872-894.
- Haradhan, M. (2018). Qualitative Research Methodology in Social Sciences and Related Subjects. *Journal of Economic Development, Environment and People*, 7(1), pp. 23-48.
- Held, D. (1987). *Models of Democracy*. Stanford: Standord University Press.
- Kallarackal, J., Jeyakumar, P., & George, SJ. (2004). Water Use of Irrigated Oil Palm at Three Different Arid Locations in Peninsular India. *Journal of Oil Palm Research*, 16(1): 59-67.
- Kinseng, R. A. (2017). Strukturugensi: Sebuah Teori Tindakan. *Sodality*, 5(2), 127-137
- Li, T, M. (2015). *Social impacts of oil palm in Indonesia: A gendered perspective from West Kalimantan*. Occasional Paper 124. Bogor, Indonesia: CIFOR.
- Lobubun, M., Raharusun, Y. A., & Anwar, I. (2022). Inkonsistensi Peraturan Perundang-Undangan dalam Penyelenggaraan Pemerintahan Daerah di Indonesia [Laws and Regulations Inconsistency in the Implementation of Regional Government of Indonesia]. *Jurnal Pembangunan Hukum Indonesia*, 4(2), 294-322.
- Luttrell C, Komarudin H, Zrust M, Pacheco P, Limberg G, Nurfatriani F, Wibowo LR, Hakim I and Pirard R. (2018). Implementing sustainability commitments for palm oil in Indonesia: Governance arrangements of sustainability initiatives involving public and private actors. *Working Paper 241*. Bogor, Indonesia: CIFOR.
- Lynch, M. J. (2020). Green Criminology and Environmental Crime: Criminology That Matters in the Age of Global Ecological Collapse. *Journal of White Collar and Corporate Crime*, 1(1) 50-61
- Lynch, M. J., Stretesky, P. B., & Long, M. A. (2020). The treadmill of production and the treadmill of law: Propositions for analyzing law, ecological disorganization and crime. *Capitalism Nature Socialism*, 31(1), 107-122.
- Mol, H. (2017). *The Politics of Palm Oil Harm: A Green Criminological Perspective*. Palgrave MacMillan
- Mustofa, M. (2007). *Kriminologi-Kajian Sosiologis Terhadap Kriminalitas, perilaku Menyimpang dan Pelanggaran Hukum (Edisi kedua) [Criminology-Sociological Studies on Crime, Deviant Behaviour, and Law Violations (2nd editions)]*. Bekasi: Sari Ilmu Pratama.
- Obidzinski, K., R. Andriani, H. Komarudin, and A. Andrianto. (2012). Environmental and social impacts of oil palm plantations and their implications for biofuel production in Indonesia. *Ecology and Society*, 17(1): 25.
- Onwuegbuzie, Leech & Collins. (2012). Qualitative Analysis Techniques for the Review of the Literature. *The Qualitative Report*, 17(56), 1-28.
- Pease, K. (1998). *Repeat Victimisation: Taking Stock*. London: Police Research Group, Home Office.
- Peluso, N. L., & Lund, C. (2011). New Frontiers of Land Control: Introduction. *Journal of Peasant Studies*, 38(4), 667-681.
- Pichler, M. (2013). People, Planet & Profit: Consumer-Oriented Hegemony and Power Relations in Palm Oil and Agrofuel Certification. *Journal of Environment & Development*, 22(4) 370-390.

- Ruggiero, V & South, N. (2013). Green Criminology and Crimes of the Economy: Theory Research and Praxis. *Critical Criminology*, 21, 359–373.
- Ruyschaert, D. (2016). *The Impact of Global Palm Oil Certification on Transnational Governance, Human Livelihoods and Biodiversity Conservation*. Toronto: Policy Matters.
- Sachiho, A, W. (2008). Pembangunan Perkebunan Kelapa Sawit di Provinsi Riau: Sebuah Tafsiran seputar Pemberdayaan Petani Kebun [Oil Palm Plantations Development in Riau Province: An Interpretation of Empowering Farmers]. *Komaba Studies in Human Geography*, 18, 1-16.
- Sawit Watch. (2015). *Catatan Singkat Akhir Tahun Perburuhan Sawit Watch 2015*. Accessed through <https://sawitwatch.or.id/2016/02/09/catatan-singkat-akhir-tahun-perburuhan-sawit-watch-2015/>
- Sikor, T., & Lund, C. (2009). Access and Property: A Question of Power and Authority. *Development and Change*, 40(1), 1-22.
- Soedomo, S. (2019). Impacts of Oil Palm Plantation on The Livelihood of The Local Communities and The Conservation Area. *Earth and Environmental Science*, 1-8. Rio de Janeiro: IOP Conference Series.
- South, N., & Beirne, P. (2007). Introduction: Approaching green criminology. In P. Beirne, & N. South, *Issues in Green Criminology: Confronting Harms against Environments, Humanity and other Animals* (pp. xiii-xxii). Columpton: Willan Publishing.
- Syahza, Nasrul dan Irianti. (2020). What's Wrong with Palm Oil, why is it Accused of Damaging the Environment? *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* 1655 (2020) 012134
- White, R. (2008). Environmental harm and crime prevention. *Trends & Issues in Crime and Criminal Justice*, 360, 1-6.
- White, R. (2011). *Transnational environmental crime: toward an eco-global criminology*. London: Routledge.
- White, R. (2013). *Environmental Harm: An eco-justice perspective*. Briston: White Press.
- White, R. (2014). Introduction: Environmental crime and eco-global criminology. In R. White, *Environmental Crime: A Reader* (pp. 1-8). Oxon: Routledge.
- White, R. (2022). *Theorising Green Criminology: Selected Essays*. Oxon: Routledge.
- Wibisono, Y. (2007). *Membedah Konsep dan Aplikasi CSR [Dissecting CSR Concepts and Applications]*. Gresik: Fascho Publishing.